

Role of GPR109A Receptor in the Efficacy of Nicotinic Acid

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ABSTRACT: Nicotinic acid is used to treat dyslipidemia from the past few decades. Nicotinic acid has the capability to increase plasma HDL cholesterol concentration, and so it is being used as a potential pharmacological agent. Nicotinic acid has an unwanted side effect called flushing, which affects the patients' compliance as this is unpleasant. With the help of receptor GPR109A for nicotinic acid it is possible to understand the underlying mechanism of action and effects of nicotinic acid, and this helped in maximizing the potential pharmacological effects of nicotinic acid and reducing the flushing side effects. GPR109A is a G protein coupled receptor which is activated by nicotinic acid (NA). The role of GPR109A receptor in the efficacy of nicotinic acid is discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Nicotinic acid has been used to treat dyslipidemia from many years and also atherosclerosis [1,2]. The antiatherosclerotic effect of nicotinic acid is observed in rabbits for the first time after the discovery of nicotinic acid's capability to lower the cholesterol by Altschul [3]. Later in the other animal experiments there was a reduction of atherosclerotic lesion seen due to nicotinic acid and its derivatives [4,5,6,7]. A combination of nicotinamide and nicotinic acid is called Niacin and vitamin B3 is used as a pharmacotherapeutic agent since 1955, which makes it the oldest lipidemic drug as it was discovered in the old years. Vitamin B3 plays an important role in the proper functioning of the central nervous system as it works on providing neuroprotection and prevents neuronal death.

The angiographic studies first showed the antiatherosclerotic effects in humans from the use of nicotinic acid and the studies showed regression of antiatherosclerosis in coronary and peripheral arteries [8,9]. Also with the help of nicotinic acid there is reduction in the cardiovascular diseases seen to have reduction [10]. Some recent studies showed that nicotinic acid has enhanced the effects of statin in reducing the risk of HDL issues. These studies also proved to slow down the atherosclerosis progression in patients with low levels of HDL.

Nicotinic acid is being used for more than fifty years as a pharmacological agent to treat dyslipidemia and is still used as an effective strategy over serum triglycerides and to increase HDL cholesterol. In the clinical trials that were randomly conducted for the first time it is observed that niacin reduced the occurrence of heart disease, by reducing the triglyceride concentrations by 27 percent and reduced the mortality rate due to CVD by 26% and myocardial infarctions by 27%. Studies also proved that niacin is also able to reduce the number of angiographically documented vascular lesions and the thickness of carotid artery intima in patients with cardiovascular disease [11,12].

The improvement in the prevention of cardiovascular issues due to niacin are mainly due to its effect on lipoprotein and blood lipid and reduction in vascular inflammation along with thrombosis [13]. Some other studies recently also proved the significance of niacin modulating serum adipokine concentrations. Researcher [14] proved that in his research that by treating obese men who have metabolic syndrome, with niacin for 6 weeks increased adiponectin serum by 54%. Investigations that are done by other researchers in support of this findings further found that the increase in adiponectin is mainly due to an increase in the HMW form of adiponectin [15]. Effects of nicotinic acid on adiponectin serum concentration are important, as it is an important biomarker of metabolic disease with insulin-sensitizing, anti-inflammatory properties. Adiponectin serum levels are usually low in obese people and are strongly associated with cardiovascular diseases. So it is proved that niacin plays a major role in increasing adiponectin serum concentration thereby reducing CVD risk. NA has a short biological half-life of 1-3 hours. Researchers [16] have developed a dissolution-controlled system for NA by encapsulating with a natural phenolic antioxidant polymer. This approach is to achieve a stable drug level in plasma with reduced fluctuations via slow drug release over an extended period of time. The F4 and F5 formulations resulted in good drug release and encapsulation efficiency. But formulation F-4 showed the release percentage of 97.74% for 11 hours.

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whereas F-5 with 97.23% for 12 hours. The results suggested that the formulated controlled-release tablets of NA through encapsulation can be effective than the conventional dosage forms and also better patient compliance

This reduction in adipose tissue with nicotinic acid administration is due to the activation of recently identified G protein coupled receptor GPR109A. A number of agonists which includes acipimox, acifran and niacin are identified to activate the receptor. From the oxidation of fatty acids ketone body β -Hydroxybutyrate (β -OHB) is produced which is also identified as endogenous ligand of the receptor. It is proved that for niacin mediated reduction of adipose tissue GPR109A is needed but the role of GPR109A in the regulation of adiponectin secretion is not known.

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF NICOTINIC ACID

In the mitochondria Niacin will undergo biochemical reactions and forms nicotinamide. Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide and NAD phosphate are formed from tryptophan shown in figure 1. The formed NAD and NADP are the niacin forms that are active which reduces to NAD (H) and NADP (H) and are formed as a cofactor in anabolic redox reactions and thus participates in catabolic redox reactions. Even though Niacin has been used though out many years, pleiotropic effect of it makes it difficult to grasp its mechanism of action completely. However based on certain effects and its targeted mechanism of action, the use of it in the human body are:

1. Capability of niacin in lowering lipid levels is very diverse and is under investigation. One of the mechanisms proposed was to mediate action of niacin's antilipolytic effect via nicotinic acid receptors. Another alternate mechanism which was recently discovered is the ability to speed up the intracellular degradation of Apo lipoprotein B (ApoB) by niacin, which contains lipoproteins like VLDL and LDL by inhibiting triglyceride synthesis. Niacin also decreases hepatic triglyceride synthesis by inhibiting diacylglycerol acyltransferase 2 (DGAT2). One suggested mechanism to increase the HDL cholesterol levels is to use niacin's ability to decrease the degradation of ApoA-I-containing lipoproteins and increase peroxisome proliferator activated receptor (PPAR γ) expression and enhances PPAR γ transcriptional activity in macrophages [17]. With the help of downregulating action of Niacin's cyclic adenosine monophosphate free fatty acid levels can be lowered. By doing this, pro-lipolytic stimuli can be reduced which is an important intracellular mediator.

Fig 1: Formation of NAD

2. Increased fasting glycemia: Using the role of niacin's responsive G protein coupled receptor (GPR109) and PFAs (plasma free fatty acids) this could be achieved. This research has identified relationship between resistance of insulin in muscles and high FFA, even though the details of mechanism are still yet to be discovered. When GPR109 is stimulated by niacin it is observed to increase the local glucose uptake in vivo intestinal cells, which may contribute to loss of glycemic control [19].
3. Aging related pathologies and process: There is an inverse relationship is found between nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) concentration vs intake of dietary niacin, even though the mechanism of action is yet to be fully

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discovered. Power of cell to undergo growth and division is lost if the intracellular NAD concentrations are reduced which could lead to cell aging and death [6]. For the protection of the genome and DNA damage repair NAD dependent enzymes like sirtuin proteins and ADP-ribose and PARP continuously provide protection. With the decrease of PARP, researchers noticed increase of cancer incidence and reactive oxygen species. Also the effects of caloric restriction to extend the life span that is mediated by sirtuins are associated with aging prematurely and other disorders like Huntington and also age associated neurological disorders in the cells with defective sirtuins [20].

4. Malignant glioma: Both in in-vivo and in-vitro niacin might exhibit glioma cell invasion. Cell migration, adhesion and polarity is carried out with the help of epithelial mesenchymal transition EMT. Even in the E-cadherin downregulation, which is an epithelial marker and upregulation of snail, and both these processes are important for the normal development of mesoderm and neural crest migration. EMT is involved. Cells are found to have EMT like processes by researcher, which not only gives the ability for them to recur but also to cause immunosuppression and cell invasion. With the help of treatment using niacin the degradation of snail, and EMT promoting transcription factor which can lead to U251 glioblastoma multiforme cell invasion, which leads to tumor invasion decrease [21,22].

NICOTINIC ACID RECEPTOR GPR109A

GPR109A which is also called as hydroxy carboxylic acid 2 receptor or also called HM74a is the receptor for nicotinic acid. The receptor GPR109 acts as mediator in expanding repertoire of therapeutic actions that has potential [23, 24]. Gi protein coupled cell surface receptors which are expressed in adipocytes and immune cells in both rodent species and human cells, and GPR109 belongs to this family. In human monocytes and adipocytes, the anti inflammatory effects of NA are seen [25, 26]. These effects are mediated via GPR109 mechanisms. These observations are also recently studied in mice, which proved that NA reduces atherosclerosis progression using GPR109 on myeloid cells which having any effect on plasma lipoproteins. This Gi protein coupled receptor is called HM74A in humans and PUMA-G in mice, which is also helpful for cardiovascular issues as it is used to modify lipoproteins in humans. This use of NA as therapeutic agent is highly due to the GPR109A activation on adipocytes surface. In spleen and lung tissues GPR109 and mRNA is expressed, but it is not yet clear in which cells the receptor is expressed and if it is functional. In the recent studies it is shown that interferon is able to induce receptor GPR109A in macrophages and prostaglandin E2 and D2 is stimulated in these cells. In the cells outside of adipose tissue, identification of functional GPR109A raised the question that if there are another cell types that carry GPR109A receptors, which can also be targeted in the therapy with NA. Some of the observations done by researchers are that NA plays an important role in atherosclerosis regression in humans alongside with its capacity to act on monocyte and macrophage as we discussed earlier and this in turn regulates proteins that are associated with cholesterol efflux, which can raise important factor that NA exerts effects via GPR109A leading to plaque regression.

Fig 2: Nicotinic acid metabolite role in flushing

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The effects of NA on human macrophage foam cells are tested by researcher [27,28] to explore their mechanism of action in lipid handling, and the confirmation that NA induces flushing response is mediated by GPR109A raised some interesting doubts like whether it will be possible to get efficacy that is beneficial without flushing induced by GPR109A and it was figured that different other formulations, drugs and GPR109A ligands have induced less flushing than NA [27,28]. So, as the diversity of GPR109A is increased in the chemical aspect it is more possible that flushing is less compared to that induced by NA. Another question raised was the involvement of GPR109A which is located outside of adipose tissue can contribute to the clinical efficacy of NA due to its flushing response.

GPR109A is highly expressed in lymphoid cells. This expression profile, coupled with the observation that in murine macrophages, GPR109A is upregulated by cytokines like IFN- γ (24), may suggest a role for GPR109A in immunity and inflammation. If this is the case, then it is interesting to speculate on whether nicotinic acid achieves any of its clinical efficacy via these cell types (e.g., at the level of the atherosclerotic plaque) and not solely via the normalization of aberrant lipoprotein profiles. Furthermore, one could speculate on a degree of analogy with the mechanism of action that results in the flushing response, for example, the generation of prostaglandins following the liberation of arachidonic acid via GPR109A stimulation.

Fig 3: Niacin and transcriptome analysis in relation to the GPR109A receptor

If this functionality of GPR109A is indeed involved in the clinical efficacy of nicotinic acid, it raises further areas for investigation, which would include determination of whether the tachyphylaxis observed in the flushing response to nicotinic acid and acipimox is observed in other immune/inflammatory cell types and whether the symptomatic relief from flushing achieved by NSAID administration has detrimental effects on some aspects of the efficacy of GPR109A agonists. NSAID treatment will not effect the lipoprotein changes that are happened with nicotinic acid, which possibly suggests the direct involvement of event mediated by GPR109A .

	EC ₅₀ (μM)	
	GPR109A	GPR109B
nicotinic acid	0,1	>100
acipimox	5,1	>100
3-hydroxybutyrate	750	25 000
1-IPBT-5-CA	>1000	0,4
acifran	1,2	7
nicotinamide	inactive	inactive
acetoacetate	>25 000	25 000

Fig 4: Structures and properties of ligands GPR109A and GPR109B

Nicotinic acid will show several side effects which might be harmless. The most common side effect of nicotinic acid is cutaneous vasodilation, most commonly in the upper half of body and the face. This effect would last for one to two hours after nicotinic acid is taken orally. This cutaneous reaction is called as flushing. This effect flushing effect the compliance of patient as it is unpleasant. Nicotinic acids dermatic formulations esters including propyl, benzyl or methyl nicotinate are the reason for the cause of dilatatory effect in blood vessels. Effects of nicotinic acid on lipid metabolism are constant over a longer period of time , opposite to that flushing will have little tolerance , which results in flushing being reduced in few weeks.

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Some studies which were done recently in a mice with deficiency of GPR109A demonstrated that flushing response due to nicotinic acid is mediated by nicotinic acid receptor [29]. Transplanting bone marrow in the GPR109A deficient animals helps with the response to nicotinic acid with cutaneous vasodilation [29]. This suggests that adipocytes are not the ones that mediates the flushing response, but the receptors on the bone marrow derived cells. Flushing response induced by nicotinic acid is induced with the activation of the receptor on epidermal immune cells and this is proved by the cutaneous reaction that has happened due to the application of skin permeable nicotinic acid esters, and this is indistinguishable from the nicotinic acid response induced by applying systematically. Another researcher has provided strong evidence in support to the fact that nicotinic acid flushing is strongly involved with epidermal Langerhans cells [30,31]. This fact is based on the observation that with increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} along with the formation of prostanooids, Langerhans cells respond to nicotinic acid and express GPR109A. Another observation seen is, flushing response is not seen in the mice which are depleted of Langerhans cells [30,31].

It has been observed that without reducing the good effects of nicotinic acid, flushing response induced by nicotinic acid can be reduced with COX inhibitors. Prostanoids, like PGD₂ or their metabolites are produced after administering nicotinic acid. It is clearly proved that nicotinic acid induced flushing response is mediated by PGD₂ and prostaglandin E₂, which dilate dermal blood vessels via the activation of DP1 and EP2/EP4 receptors, from the studies of Pharmacological and genetic evidence. From these research data a nicotinic acid induced response model has emerged [32-37].

Increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} through the GPR109A activation on epidermal Langerhans cells is seen using nicotinic acid. As a result Ca^{2+} phospholipase A₂ is activated and then arachidonic acid is formed which is then further metabolized to PGD₂ and prostaglandin E₂. Both the prostanoids are now able to induce the dilation of blood vessels in the dermis upper layers through activation of Gi coupled receptors.

Conclusion: GPR109A represents a molecular target that is exciting. Further examination of this receptor needs to be done in order to understand mechanism of action of nicotinic acid and thereby helping increase the therapeutic action of nicotinic acid. The recent studies have provided information on role of the receptor GPR109A in the therapeutic effects of nicotinic acid, but more research needs to be done to elevate the understanding of its role.

REFERENCES

- 1) Carlson LA. Nicotinic acid: the broad-spectrum lipid drug. A 50th anniversary review. *J Intern Med.* 2005;258(2):94–114.
- 2) Meyers CD, Kamanna VS, Kashyap ML. Niacin therapy in atherosclerosis. *Curr Opin Lipidol.* 2004;15(6):659–665.
- 3) Altschul R. Die Beeinflussung des Blutcholesterinspiegels und der experimentellen Atherosklerose durch Nikotinsäure. *Ztschr f Kreislaufforsch.* 1956;45:453–460.
- 4) Brattsand R, Lundholm L. The effect of nicotinic acid and pentaerythritolteranicotinate upon experimental atherosclerosis in the rabbit. *Atherosclerosis.* 1971;14(1):91–105.
- 5) Lundholm L, Jacobsson L, Brattsand R, Magnusson O. Influence of nicotinic acid, niceritrol and beta-pyridylcarbinol on experimental hyperlipidemia and atherosclerosis in mini-pigs. *Atherosclerosis.* 1978;29(2):217–239.
- 6) Parwaresch MR, Haacke H, Mader C. Efficacy of hypolipidemic treatment in inhibition of experimental atherosclerosis: the effect of nicotinic acid and related compounds. *Atherosclerosis.* 1978;31(4):395–401.
- 7) Weitzel G, Wahl P, Buddecke E. Anti-atherosclerotic action of vitamin A compounds, nicotinic acid, beta-pyridyl compounds and arachidonic acid. *Hoppe Seylers Z Physiol Chem.* 1962;327:109–127.
- 8) West C-R. Regression of atherosclerosis during nicotinic acid therapy: a study in man by means of repeated arteriographies. In: Altschul R, ed. *Niacin In Vascular Disorders And Hyperlipemia*. Springfield, Illinois, USA: Charles C. Thomas Publisher, LTD; 1964:245–262.
- 9) Blankenhorn DH, Johnson RL, Nessim SA, Azen SP, Sanmarco ME, Selzer RH. The Cholesterol Lowering Atherosclerosis Study (CLAS): design, methods, and baseline results. *Control Clin Trials.* 1987;8(4):356–387. View this article via: PubMed CrossRef Google Scholar
- 10) Knopp R. Evaluating niacin in its various forms. *Am J Cardiol* 86: 51L–56L, 2000.
- 11) Taylor AJ, Sullenberger LE, Lee HJ, Lee JK, Grace KA. Arterial Biology for the Investigation of the Treatment Effects of Reducing Cholesterol (ARBITER) 2: a double-blind, placebo-controlled study of extended-release niacin on atherosclerosis progression in secondary prevention patients treated with statins. *Circulation* 110: 3512–3517, 2004.
- 12) Knopp R, Ginsberg J, Albers JJ. Contrasting effects of unmodified and time-release forms of niacin on lipoproteins in hyperlipidemic subjects: clues to mechanism of action of niacin. *Metabolism* 34: 642–650, 1985.
- 13) Westphal S, Borucki K, Taneva E, Makarova R, Luley C. Extended-release niacin raises adiponectin and leptin. *Atherosclerosis* 193: 361–365, 2007.

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- 14) Plaisance EP, Grandjean PW, Brunson BL, Judd RL. Increased total and high-molecular weight adiponectin after extended-release niacin. *Metabolism* 57: 404–409, 2008
- 15) Manne, R., & Devarajan, A. (2020). Development of Nicotinic Acid Controlled Release Tablets with Natural Phenolic Antioxidant Polymer by Encapsulation Technique. *Journal of Natural Remedies*, 20(4), 139-151. [[Google Scholar](#)]
- 16) Canner PL, et al. Fifteen year mortality in Coronary Drug Project patients: long-term benefit with niacin. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 1986;8(6):1245–1255. View this article via: [PubMed CrossRef Google Scholar](#)
- 17) Gille A, Bodor ET, Ahmed K, Offermanns S. Nicotinic acid: pharmacological effects and mechanisms of action. *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol.* 2008;48:79-106. [[PubMed](#)]
- 18) Montecucco F, Quercioli A, Dallegri F, Viviani GL, Mach F. New evidence for nicotinic acid treatment to reduce atherosclerosis. *Expert Rev Cardiovasc Ther.* 2010 Oct;8(10):1457-67. [[PubMed](#)]
- 19) Meyer-Ficca M, Kirkland JB. Niacin. *Adv Nutr.* 2016 May;7(3):556-8. [PMC free article] [[PubMed](#)]
- 20) Li J, Qu J, Shi Y, Perfetto M, Ping Z, Christian L, Niu H, Mei S, Zhang Q, Yang X, Wei S. Nicotinic acid inhibits glioma invasion by facilitating Snail1 degradation. *Sci Rep.* 2017 Mar 03;7:43173. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- 21) Yang X, Mei S, Niu H, Li J. Nicotinic acid impairs assembly of leading edge in glioma cells. *Oncol Rep.* 2017 Aug;38(2):829-836. [PMC free article] [[PubMed](#)]
- 22) Offermanns S (2006) The nicotinic acid receptor GPR109A (HM74A or PUMA-G) as a new therapeutic target. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences* 27: 384–390. View Article [Google Scholar](#)
- 23) Digby JE, Ruparelia N, Choudhury RP (2012) Niacin in Cardiovascular Disease: Recent Preclinical and Clinical Developments. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 32: 582–588. View Article [Google Scholar](#)
- 24) Digby JE, McNeill E, Dyar OJ, Lam V, Greaves DR, et al. (2010) Anti-inflammatory effects of nicotinic acid in adipocytes demonstrated by suppression of fractalkine, RANTES, and MCP-1 and upregulation of adiponectin. *Atherosclerosis* 209: 89–95. View Article [Google Scholar](#)
- 25) Digby JE, Martinez F, Jefferson A, Ruparelia N, Chai JT, et al. (2012) Anti-Inflammatory Effects of Nicotinic Acid in Human Monocytes Are Mediated by GPR109A Dependent Mechanisms. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol* 32: 669–676.
- 26) Lukasova M, Malaval C, Gille A, Kero J, Offermanns S (2011) Nicotinic acid inhibits progression of atherosclerosis in mice through its receptor GPR109A expressed by immune cells. *Journal of Clinical Investigation* 121: 1163–1173.
- 27) Guyton, JR. Extended-release niacin for modifying the lipoprotein profile. *Expert Opin. Pharmacother.* 2004. 5:1385-1398. View this article via: [PubMed Google Scholar](#)
- 28) Tornvall, P, Walldius, G. A comparison between nicotinic acid and acipimox in hypertriglyceridaemia – effects on serum lipids, lipoproteins, glucose tolerance and tolerability. *J. Intern. Med.* 1991. 230:415-421. View this article via: [PubMed Google Scholar](#)
- 29) Schaub, A, Futterer, A, Pfeffer, K. PUMA-G, an IFN-gamma-inducible gene in macrophages is a novel member of the seven transmembrane spanning receptor superfamily. *Eur. J. Immunol.* 2001. 31:3714-3725. View this article via: [PubMed Google Scholar](#)
- 30) Carlson, LA. Nicotinic acid and inhibition of fat mobilizing lipolysis. Present status of effects on lipid metabolism. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 1978. 109:225-238.
- 31) Benyó Z, Gille A, Kero J, Csiky M, Suchankova MC, Nusing RM et al. (2005). GPR109A (PUMA-G/HM74A) mediates nicotinic acid-induced flushing. *J Clin Invest* 115: 3634–3640.
- 32) Maciejewski-Lenoir D, Richman JG, Hakak Y, Gaidarov I, Behan DP, Connolly DT (2006). Langerhans cells release prostaglandin D2 in response to nicotinic acid. *J Invest Dermatol* 126: 2637–2646.
- 33) Benyó Z, Gille A, Bennett CL, Clausen BE, Offermanns S (2006). Nicotinic acid-induced flushing is mediated by activation of epidermal langerhans cells. *Mol Pharmacol* 70: 1844–1849.
- 34) Stern, R. H. (2007). The role of nicotinic acid metabolites in flushing and hepatotoxicity. *Journal of clinical lipidology*, 1(3), 191-193.
- 35) Bodor, E. T., & Offermanns, S. (2008). Nicotinic acid: an old drug with a promising future. *British journal of pharmacology*, 153(S1), S68-S75.
- 36) Plaisance, E. P., Lukasova, M., Offermanns, S., Zhang, Y., Cao, G., & Judd, R. L. (2009). Niacin stimulates adiponectin secretion through the GPR109A receptor. *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 296(3), E549-E558.